

In this frame from the 2008 video, the wings are nearly fully extended but poorly resolved. The direct and reflected images of the bird are circled. The apparent midpoint between the images corresponds approximately to the location of the projection of the position of the bird onto the surface of the bayou as marked by the red arrow.



In this frame from the 2008 video, the wings are only partially extended but well resolved. The direct and reflected images of the bird are circled. The apparent midpoint between the images corresponds approximately to the location of the projection of the position of the bird onto the surface of the bayou as marked by the red arrow.



In this image, Tommy Tuma of the Louisiana Department of Wildlife and Fisheries is holding a 24-inch reference object, which was cut from a yardstick, near the location of the bird in the 2008 video when it passed near a tree. The three images on the lower left are from the video. The other image is of a Belted Kingfisher, which has prominent dorsal field marks.



In this image, Tommy Tuma is holding the reference object, while Wayne Higginbotham, also of the Louisiana Department of Wildlife and Fisheries, holds the boat in position near the flight path of the bird in the 2008 video.



In this image, a dashed rectangle with the same width as the reference object has been added.



This image from the video has been scaled using trees that appear in the scene. By going into full screen mode and toggling back and forth between this slide and the previous slide, it is easy to see that the image has been scaled properly. The white rectangle was copied onto this image without changing its size.



This slide is identical to the fifth slide.



This image from the video has been scaled using trees that appear in the scene. By going into full screen mode and toggling back and forth between this slide and the previous slide, it is easy to see that the image has been scaled properly. The white rectangle was copied onto this image without changing its size.



This slide is the same as the previous slide but with the brightness and contrast adjusted to enhance the wings. It is clear that the wingspan is well above 24 inches.

